

Development and Structural Evaluation of Cement-less UHPC for Sustainable Concrete Applications New

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) is created for research application No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/148 "Development and Structural Evaluation of Cement-less UHPC for Sustainable Concrete Applications". supported by Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral Research" of the Specific Objective 1.1.1 "Strengthening research and innovative capacities and introduction of advanced technologies in the common R&D system" of the European Union's Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027. The main goal of this postdoctoral project is the development of cement-less ultra-high performance concrete (CL-UHPC) using ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBFS) replacement and wheat straw ash (WSA) as a cost-efficient cement and silica fume replacements, lime-based activator with calcium formate (CF) accelerator, and recycled steel fiber (RSF) as structural reinforcement. While designed to offer a sustainable and economical alternative, the long-term performance of CL-UHPC still requires further investigation. Additionally, its fire spalling behavior, a known concern for UHPC, will be assessed for the first time in this study. Two strategies to mitigate fire spalling will be used: a two-stage hot air curing process and the inclusion of polypropylene fibers (PF). The research will investigate the bond strength of lap spliced bars in CL-UHPC by testing reinforced concrete beams, whereas OpenSees shall be employed to model them. Existing development length models will be assessed, and nonlinear fiber-based modeling will be conducted using OpenSees. Additionally, the structural application of CL-UHPC will be explored in RC deep beams. ABAQUS will be utilized for numerical modeling to analyze the performance of deep beams.

The main objectives of the project will be:

- 1) Optimization of the mix proportions of CL-UHPC: development of a novel CL-UHPC composition by integrating WSA and RSF; identification of the optimal mix proportions by evaluating compressive strength, uniaxial tensile strength, and flowability.
- 2) Assessment of the durability of CL-UHPC: evaluation of the CL-UHPC formulations by measuring resistivity, porosity, sorptivity, and resistance to chloride migration to assess the quality of the cementitious materials.
- 3) Evaluation of the fire endurance of CL-UHPC: investigation of the fire-spalling behavior of CL-UHPC; assessment using two options - (1) two-stage hot air curing process and (2) addition of PF.
- 4) Investigation of bond behavior of lap spliced bars in CL-UHPC: assessment of the bond behavior and existing development equations of lap spliced bars in CL-UHPC; tests with varying parameters such as lap splice length and cover-to-diameter ratio.
- 5) Exploration of the performance of CL-UHPC in deep beams: examination of the shear span-to-depth ratio and the size of circular web openings; ABAQUS calculations to predict the response of CL-UHPC with and without openings.
- 6) Calculations of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA): evaluation of the environmental impacts associated with the raw material extraction, production, use, and disposal of CL-UHPC.

Research project will be implemented at Institute of Sustainable Building Materials and Engineering Systems, Riga Technical University (Latvia).

The purpose of the DMP is to outline the strategy for data collection, storing, and sharing at all the stages of research project implementation while ensuring compliance with the legal and ethical requirements. DMP will include bibliographic and experimental data arranged in datasets distinguished by relevant research activities.

Funder

European Commission

Grant

"Post-doctoral Research"

Researchers

Maris Rundans (0000-0002-5801-1146)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Development and Structural Evaluation of Cement-less UHPC for Sustainable Concrete Applications New](#)

Description:

This Data Management Plan (DMP) is created for research application No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/148 "Development and Structural Evaluation of Cement-less UHPC for Sustainable Concrete Applications". supported by Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral Research" of the Specific Objective 1.1.1 "Strengthening research and innovative capacities and introduction of advanced technologies in the common R&D system" of the European Union's Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027. The main goal of this postdoctoral project is the development of cement-less ultra-high performance concrete (CL-UHPC) using ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBFS) replacement and wheat straw ash (WSA) as a cost-efficient cement and silica fume replacements, lime-based activator with calcium formate (CF) accelerator, and recycled steel fiber (RSF) as structural reinforcement. While designed to offer a sustainable and economical alternative, the long-term performance of CL-UHPC still requires further investigation. Additionally, its fire spalling behavior, a known concern for UHPC, will be assessed for the first time in this study. Two strategies to mitigate fire spalling will be used: a two-stage hot air curing process and the inclusion of polypropylene fibers (PF). The research will investigate the bond strength of lap spliced bars in CL-UHPC by testing reinforced concrete beams, whereas OpenSees shall be employed to model them. Existing development length models will be assessed, and nonlinear fiber-based modeling will be conducted using OpenSees. Additionally, the structural application of CL-UHPC will be explored in RC deep beams. ABAQUS will be utilized for numerical modeling to analyze the performance of deep beams.

The main objectives of the project will be:

- 1) Optimization of the mix proportions of CL-UHPC: development of a novel CL-UHPC composition by integrating WSA and RSF; identification of the optimal mix proportions by evaluating compressive strength, uniaxial tensile strength, and flowability.

2) Assessment of the durability of CL-UHPC: evaluation of the CL-UHPC formulations by measuring resistivity, porosity, sorptivity, and resistance to chloride migration to assess the quality of the cementitious materials.

3) Evaluation of the fire endurance of CL-UHPC: investigation of the fire-spalling behavior of CL-UHPC; assessment using two options - (1) two-stage hot air curing process and (2) addition of PF.

4) Investigation of bond behavior of lap spliced bars in CL-UHPC: assessment of the bond behavior and existing development equations of lap spliced bars in CL-UHPC; tests with varying parameters such as lap splice length and cover-to-diameter ratio.

5) Exploration of the performance of CL-UHPC in deep beams: examination of the shear span-to-depth ratio and the size of circular web openings; ABAQUS calculations to predict the response of CL-UHPC with and without openings.

6) Calculations of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA): evaluation of the environmental impacts associated with the raw material extraction, production, use, and disposal of CL-UHPC.

Research project will be implemented at Institute of Sustainable Building Materials and Engineering Systems, Riga Technical University (Latvia).

The purpose of the DMP is to outline the strategy for data collection, storing, and sharing at all the stages of research project implementation while ensuring compliance with the legal and ethical requirements. DMP will include bibliographic and experimental data arranged in datasets distinguished by relevant research activities.

Researchers:

[Maris Rundans \(0000-0002-5801-1146\)](#)

Organizations:

[Riga Technical University](#)

Contact: [Rundans Maris \(maris.rundans@rtu.lv\)](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#)

Grants: "Post-doctoral Research"

Project: 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/148 "Development and Structural Evaluation of Cement-less UHPC for Sustainable Concrete Applications"

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-12-01

4. Templates

Descriptions

Bibliographic data regarding state-of-the-art of cement-less UHPC

This dataset contains bibliographic data for scientific publications regarding cement-less and geopolymer substituted UHPC. The data (authors and their affiliations, title, journal, volume, publication date, abstract, etc.) are retrieved from Web of Science database from 01/01/2015 to 30/06/2025. The dataset is manually reviewed and edited to exclude errors or irrelevancies and to add relevant comments if required. The dataset is intended to generate analytical and statistical data regarding research activities related to cement-less UHPC to be used in scientific reviews and reports.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of dataset is to provide up-to-date information regarding other research activities towards cement-less UHPC development. Custom

commentaries regarding content of the entry may be included for added relevance.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Aggregate data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

5

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

This bibliographic data collection is considered unique to this project.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Other researchers working on similar topic.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

<https://www.dublincore.org/>

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Data will be open accessible after the end of the project.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo is an open repository developed by CERN that supports multiple data types and is suitable for all scientific disciplines.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Any modern and up-to-date Internet Browser (Chrome, Firefox, Edge, etc.)

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-07-16

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2030-07-16

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Paid from indirect project expenses.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Maris Rundans (0000-0002-5801-1146)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Paid from indirect project expenses.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

National laws

Powered by

